

ENGLISH LANGUAGE ANXIETY IN CLASS ORAL PRESENTATION OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE NEW NORMAL

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ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that anxious individuals may experience difficulties in speaking fluently and accurately (Horwitz et al., 2019). From this perspective, this study is led to determine the experiences of students' language anxiety during class oral presentations. A convergent parallel mixed method was employed. It involved 143 participants who were selected through stratified random sampling and the use of applied statistical tools, such as frequency counts and percentage, weighted mean, Pearson's r correlation, independent sample t -test, and ANOVA. In addition, thematic analysis for basic qualitative inquiry was utilized. Data collection was conducted using a standardized questionnaire and a researcher-made interview questionnaire for the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). This study found a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety. On the other hand, there is a significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when grouped according to profile. Furthermore, the results of the study showed that participants perceived higher anxiety levels during class oral presentations. Subsequently, qualitative data revealed the following findings: a lack of confidence to speak English during oral recitations; afraid of being criticized by peers; uncontrollable fear of performing; and feeling worried about being given low grades. Based on these

findings, the following are recommended: intervention program with emphasis on modified authentic assessments; school-based policies; nation-wide training for curriculum experts, administrators, teachers, parents, school guidance counselors, and students. Henceforth, the details about the peripheral issues being identified may lead the learners to be provided with significant landscapes of learning in developing their communicative competence in English.

Keywords: *Anxiety in English classes, authentic assessment for language, class oral presentations, communicative competence, secondary language anxiety*

INTRODUCTION

Language anxiety is considered one of the problems for language learners in achieving proficiency in a foreign language (Indrianty, 2016). Similarly, language anxiety has a “negative impact on the student’s performance, attitudes, emotional state, and enjoyment of the language learning experience (Selvam et al., 2016). These emphasized that learners may experience increased stress and discomfort, hindering their ability to learn and use the language effectively.

In the context of English as a Second Language (ESL) in the Philippines, classroom practices and the identity of the teacher could have an impact on language anxiety, especially when it comes to oral presentations. Teacher identity and classroom practices impact language anxiety among Filipino ESL learners during oral presentations. Teachers who were strict, critical, or had limited English proficiency were more likely to increase students’ anxiety levels (Tumapon, 2019).

Rudiansyah et al. (2016) stated that many factors trigger anxiety in students at school. The influence of demands, competition, and disasters that occur in life can impact physical and psychological health (Pratama, 2022). Likewise, the attitude and treatment of less friendly, harsh, fierce, and less competent teachers can also cause anxiety in students, which comes from the teacher factor. Classroom setting, engagement, inappropriate teaching content, and teaching methods adopted by teachers also cause students anxiety (Alrabai, 2014).

In addition, Mestan (2017) explained that numerous studies pointed at anxiety as the culprit of negative repercussions on language learners’ production and reception skills, as well as the level of anxiety developing as language learners proceed with unrehearsed oral speaking in public. The results explained that students’ speaking anxiety was due to their self-deprecation and fear of making a mistake while speaking in front of each other.

Furthermore, since the COVID-19 pandemic affected the world in late December 2019, learning and teaching paradigms have changed dramatically (Alzamil, 2021). It undeniably affects the education sector (Erkan, 2019). The advent of online learning and virtual classrooms, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has highlighted the importance of communication skills on another level (Don et al., 2022). Technology plays a significant role in the new normal Covid 19 (Jordan, 2020). In the new normal of education, which deals with both online and face-to-face interactions, it is important to explore the factors that cause learners' anxiety during oral presentations.

However, Filipino students often struggle and feel nervous when they have oral presentations in English class. This phenomenon can be attributed to various factors, including the influence of the educational system, cultural attitudes towards language learning, and individual learner characteristics. A study conducted by Yacat (2018) revealed that Filipino students tend to exhibit high levels of anxiety when speaking in English, particularly in formal settings such as class presentations. This anxiety is often linked to the fear of making mistakes and being judged by others, which can be exacerbated by the emphasis on correctness and fluency in English language education in the Philippines (Llurda, 2018). These findings highlight the need for educators to be aware of the challenges faced by Filipino students and to provide support and strategies to help them manage their anxiety and improve their oral communication skills in English.

As such, it is for this reason that the researchers decided to conduct the study titled English Language Anxiety in Class Oral Presentation of Junior High School Students in the New Normal. This study aimed to determine the experiences of students' language anxiety during class oral presentations. Knowing that language anxiety can impede student speaking and learning in English is something that caught the researcher's interest in conducting this study.

The study sought to describe the demographic profile of the participants and investigated whether there was a significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when group according to profile and a significant relationship between the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety and their academic performance in English. The findings of this study would be beneficial to teachers, parents, administrators, psychologists, and, most importantly, to the students. The result of this study would also serve as the basis for an intervention program.

Research Questions

The primary concern of this study was to determine the experiences of students' language anxiety during class oral presentations of the Grade 7 students of Saint James High School of Buenavista, Agusan Inc., along with the factors of secondary English language classroom anxiety as the basis for the educational intervention program.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex;
 - 1.2 type of school graduated; and
 - 1.3 preferred mode of communication?
2. What is the academic performance of the participants in English?
3. What is the level of secondary language classroom anxiety among Grade 7 students in terms of:
 - 3.1 communication apprehension;
 - 3.2 test anxiety;
 - 3.3 fear of negative evaluation; and
 - 3.4 anxiety of English classes?
4. Is there a significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when group according to profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety?
6. What are the participants experiences of English language anxiety in class oral presentations?
7. Based on the results of the study, what intervention program can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, research locale, research participants, data gathering procedure, quantification of data, and statistical treatment that were applied in analyzing the gathered data.

Research Design

This study utilized a convergent parallel mixed-methods research design. The study made use of a quantitative method that involved administering an adapted survey questionnaire to gather numerical data on the variables. Simultaneously, the qualitative method employed a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) for an in-depth analysis of the participants experiences towards language anxiety in class oral presentations. Thematic analysis is used to analyze and interpret the qualitative data, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the participants experiences of language anxiety and their coping mechanisms in dealing with English class oral presentations. An intervention program is designed to support teachers and students in maintaining effective strategies for coping with anxiety when speaking in English.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at one of the private secondary schools in Buenavista, Agusan del Norte, which is Saint James High School of Buenavista, Agusan Inc. St. James High School of Buenavista, Agusan Inc., is a private school under the Roman Catholic order, founded by the priests of the Missionaries of the Sacred Heart, located in Buenavista, Agusan del Norte, and run by the Diocese of Butuan (Butuan, Philippines). It is the only Catholic school in the town. There are 1700 enrolled junior and senior high school students. It has 54 active teachers and four strands and includes technical and vocational education offered. The participants of this study were the 143 Grade 7 students of Saint James High School of Buenavista, Agusan Inc.

Participants of The Study

The participants of this study were the 143 Grade 7 students of Saint James High School of Buenavista, Agusan Inc., as shown in the table below. The Grade 7 students were the participants to the study since they are the first to deal with a higher level of proficiency in the English subject, in which they experience higher anxiety in terms of speaking the target language in the class.

Sampling Design

There are 277 Junior High School students at Saint James High School of Buenavista, Agusan, Inc. For administrative considerations, only 75% of the total population were considered participants. Thus, only 143 Junior High School students were involved in the study. To ensure that every grade level would be represented in the study, stratified sampling was applied with a formula of $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$ following the Slovin's formula.

In selecting the participants of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), there were ten respondents who were interviewed. The researcher gathered the names of the participants from the Grade 7 advisers and codes each of them. According to Morgan (2011), it is the average level and appropriate to ask at least six to ten participants in a focus group discussion.

Instruments of The Study

The study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire as a source of information to acquire the needed information. The questionnaire in this study consists of two parts. The first part is all about the student profile, which includes the respondents' sex, type of school they graduated in Elementary level, preferred mode of communication, and their academic performance. The second part is the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), developed by Horwitz et al. (1986). The number of items is organized into different components: (1) Communication Apprehension: Item 1,9,14,18,24,27,29,32; (2) Test Anxiety: Item 2,8,10,19,21; (3) Fear of Negative Evaluation: Item 3,7,13,15,20,23,25,31,33; and (4) Anxiety of English Classes: Item 4,5,6,11,12,16,17,22,26,28,30. This study includes a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) to

determine the experiences of students with English language anxiety in class oral presentations. The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FCLAS) was the research tool used in gathering the data.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the validity and reliability of the research questionnaire, the researchers adapted the research instrument and submitted a copy of the adapted questionnaire to the psychologist and guidance counselor, whose expertise is relevant to language anxiety. After retrieving the comments and suggestions from the experts, the researchers then presented and gathered the data from the participants. Then the data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by a statistician for their reliability coefficient.

Data Gathering Procedure

To gather the data, the researchers made use of the adapted questionnaire and employed the following strategies:

Entry Protocol Phase. Before the conduct of the study, the researchers secured a letter of permission. It was signed and granted by the School Director and School Principal of Saint James High School of Buenavista, Agusan Inc. After that, the said letter was presented to the Junior High Coordinator, and then followed by the Grade 7 advisers.

Administration and Retrieval Phase. The researchers personally administered the research instrument. Before the administration, the researchers conducted a brief orientation with the participants on the nature of the study and assured them that the data they provided would be treated with the utmost confidentiality. After the administration, the researchers then collected the questionnaires that the participants answered.

Organization Phase. After the successful retrieval of the research instrument, participants responses were organized.

Data Interpretation Phase. After organizing the students' responses, the data was submitted to a statistician for analysis.

Thematic Analysis. Thematic analysis is employed to analyze the data on the experiences of the learner in dealing with language anxiety in class oral presentation. Brau and Clarke (2006) stressed thematic analysis as a method to find and analyze emerging themes in a dataset to unravel the themes, meanings, and essences of an individual's experiences. In the thematic analysis, the researchers took the following steps: a) familiarizing with the data with the transcribed information; b) generating initial codes; c) looking for/or searching for themes; d) reviewing the identified themes before defining the themes produced from this process; and e) writing thematic analysis.

Statistical Treatment

To analyze the data gathered, the researchers made use of the following statistical tools:

Frequency counts and percentages. These were used to determine the demographic profile and academic performance of the participants.

Weighted Mean. This was employed to determine the level of anxiety of the participants, which affects the factors of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety.

Pearson's r Correlation. This was utilized to determine the academic performance of the participants in English.

Independent Sample t-test. This was utilized to determine the level of secondary language classroom anxiety among Grade 7 students.

ANOVA. This was utilized to determine the significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when grouped according to profile.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the data gathered through the research instruments used in the study. It provides the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data presented in tables with a textual explanation.

Research Question 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Table 1 presents the frequency and percent distribution of the sex, type of school graduated, and preferred mode of communication.

Table 1.

Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Sex, Type of School Graduated, and Preferred Mode of Communication of the Participants

Group	Subgroup	Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	79	55.25
	Female	64	44.76
Type of School Graduated	Public	103	72.03
	Private	40	27.97
Mode of Communication	Verbal	67	46.85
	Written	31	21.68
	Audio	29	20.28
	Visual	11	7.69
	Nonverbal	5	3.50

In terms of sex between males and females, it can be seen that 55.25% of the total of 79 participants are males, while 44.76% of the total of 64 participants are females. This implies that the majority of the participants are males. Ritchie (2019) reported that in every country, births are male-based; hence, it is expected that males will also dominate the schools in terms of population. Therefore, whether English as a second language (ESL) students learning English will gain or learning efficiency due to their gender differences has become a significant issue in ESL instruction.

In terms of type of school graduated during their sixth-grade level, it is notable that 72.03% of the total of 103 participants went to public school, while 27.97% of the total of 40 participants went to private school. This implies that the majority of participants went to public school during sixth grade level. English Language Learners (ELLs) face a challenge in acquiring good speaking skills, which requires consistent practice both inside and outside the classroom (Rao, 2019).

In terms of the preferred mode of communication of the participants, the highest has a percentage of 46.85% preferred verbal communication out of 67 participants. While the lowest has a 3.50% preferred mode of non-verbal communication. The findings imply that the preferred mode of communication of the participants is verbal communication. Nair (2023) stated that there are five types of communication: verbal, non-verbal, written, audio or aural, and visual. It was found that causes of speaking anxiety among foreign language learners differ in terms of the mode and context of speaking (Tercan and Dikilitas, 2015).

In addition, it was also emphasized in the study of Hefel (2022) that active participation in student-led discussion impacted students' engagement. Students were more engaged during the discussions through talking and asking questions (Dykstra-Steinbrenner & Watson (2015). Thus, by addressing these issues and implementing appropriate strategies, educators can support students in developing their oral communication skills and reducing their communication apprehension (Chentez et al., 2019).

Research Question 2. Academic Performance of the Participants in English

Table 2 presents the frequency and percent distribution of the academic performance of the participants based on their grade in English subject.

Table 2.

Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Academic Performance of the Participants

Grading Scale	Verbal Description	Frequency	Percent
90-100	Outstanding	40	27.97
85-89	Very Satisfactory	42	29.37
80-84	Satisfactory	46	32.17
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	15	10.49
Below 74	Did not meet expectation	-	-

In terms of the academic performance of the participants, it can be seen that the highest has a percentage of 32.17% which is interpreted as satisfactory of the total of 46 participants. While, the lowest has a percentage of 10.49% which is interpreted as fairly satisfactory of the total of 15 participants.

This finding is supported by Gawi (2020) stated that students who perform poorly in English language classes and assessments feel high levels of anxiety. Moreover, a study conducted by Grieve et al. (2021) and Nurwahyuni (2019) highlighted how public speaking anxiety can hinder academic progress and emphasized the need for universities to recognize and address this widespread problem.

This finding is contrary to Li (2020), it was found that emotional intelligence positively predicts academic success in a variety of educational settings. Previous research has shown that emotional intelligence communication (EIC) can predict pupils' academic performance in the future (Ran et al., 2022).

Research Question 3. Language Anxiety in Communication Apprehension of English as a Second Language (ESL) Learners in Classroom Setting

Table 3 shows the level of secondary language classroom anxiety among the participants in terms of communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and anxiety of English classes.

Table 3.1

Level of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety Among Grade 7 Students in Terms of Communication Apprehension

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. I never feel quite sure of myself when I am speaking in English.	3.55	Agree	Anxious
9. I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation in language class.	3.62	Agree	Anxious
14. I would not be nervous speaking English with native speakers.	3.56	Agree	Anxious
18. I feel confident when I speak in English in my language class.	3.55	Agree	Anxious
24. I feel very self-conscious about speaking English in front of the other students.	3.56	Agree	Anxious
27. I get nervous and confused when I am speaking in my language class.	3.78	Agree	Anxious
29. I get nervous when I don't understand every word the language teacher says.	3.56	Agree	Anxious
32. I would probably feel comfortable around native speakers of English.	3.55	Agree	Anxious
Average	3.59	Agree	Anxious

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Neutral, 3.50-4.49-Agree, 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree

As gleaned from the table 3.1, the highest weighted mean is 3.78, which can be interpreted as anxious. This shows that learners are anxious to speak during their language class. This also implies that learners experience fear when speaking the target language. On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean is 3.55, which can be interpreted as anxious. This deals with learners experiencing apprehension about learning and speaking the target language.

The overall weighted mean of the extent of language anxiety in terms of communication apprehension is 3.59, which can be interpreted as anxious. This means that learners are afraid to speak the target language in class because they are doubtful about speaking the English language. This suggests that for the majority of respondents, speaking and learning English can be a source of anxiety or discomfort in various contexts.

This finding is supported by the study of Gabejan (2021), noting that learners who struggle with low levels of self-confidence in the speaking classroom will consequently have less opportunity to practice, resulting in difficulty expressing themselves. Similarly, a study conducted by Shukor and Madzlan (2022), revealed that the fear of speaking in an unfamiliar language is often due to a lack of confidence that can potentially hinder learners' ability to improve their fluency and eventually increase apprehension.

This finding is contrary to Kurniawan (2016), revealed that practicing is a strategy that can be implemented by students to solve their problems in anxiety in oral presentation. The study also found ways students deal with their anxiety in presentation are preparation before presentation, relaxation, positive thinking, peer seeking and focus. Similarly, Blegur et al. (2023) stated that consistent practice of oral presentation skills can improve the precision of the information conveyed, the effectiveness of communication and the articulation of speech.

This finding is also supported by the participant's statements shared his struggles as non-English expert saying that,

“Katong time na magoral recitation mi, tas nakulbaan ko og maayo ahh... tas wala na nuon ko naka- perform kay mahadlok man ko mo-storya og English, basin ijudge kos akong mga classmate.” [That time when we were going to do oral recitation, I was so nervous that I didn't perform because I was afraid that my classmates would judge me if I spoke in English.]- I1, L14-16

Furthermore, the utterances above validated claims of participant fear of making mistakes, worrying about mispronouncing words, using incorrect grammar, or not being able to express themselves clearly, which can lead to a lack of confidence in performing in front of the class.

The findings above are similar to the study conducted by Jalleh and Mahfoodh (2021) found that limited opportunities to speak English and attitudes towards English in the students' society can potentially contribute to high levels of communication apprehension. Thus, it is evident that diverse environmental and personal factors, such as poor self-esteem, a lack of language proficiency, and a demanding learning environment, contribute to the anxiety experienced by learners.

Table 3.2 shows the level of secondary language classroom anxiety of the participants in terms of fear of negative evaluation in class oral presentations.

Table 3.2
Level of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety Among Grade 7 Students in Terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
3. I tremble when I know that I'm going to be called on in language class.	3.72	Agree	Anxious
7. I keep thinking that the other students are better at language than I am.	3.72	Agree	Anxious
13. It embarrasses me to volunteer answers in my language class.	3.77	Agree	Anxious
15. I get upset when I don't understand what the teacher is correcting.	3.16	Neutral	Mildly Anxious
20. I can feel my heart pounding when I'm going to be called on in language class.	3.78	Agree	Anxious
23. I always feel that the other students speak English better than I do.	3.74	Agree	Anxious
25. Language class moves so quickly that I worry about being left behind.	3.76	Agree	Anxious
31. I am afraid that the other students in the class will laugh at me when I speak in English.	3.80	Agree	Anxious
33. I get nervous when the language teacher asks questions that I haven't prepared for in advance.	3.71	Agree	Anxious
Average	3.68	Agree	Anxious

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Neutral, 3.50-4.49-Agree, 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree

The table 3.2 presents that the highest weighted mean is 3.80, which can be interpreted as anxious. This means that learners are afraid of being judged by their peers when speaking the target language. Then, the lowest weighted mean is 3.16, which can be interpreted as mildly anxious, it means that learners are not that upset when the teacher corrects them in language class. This shows that they are willing to be corrected by their teachers and accept criticism. The overall weighted mean of the extent of language anxiety in terms of fear of negative evaluation is 3.68, which can be interpreted as anxious.

Similarly, Khan (2015), who concludes in his study that most classrooms generate higher levels of anxiety if students feel evaluated or stressed because "they are judged, their mistakes are highlighted, and their grades are affected" when interacting in speech. Thus, in delivering an oral presentation, students will experience a different level of speaking anxiety.

In contrast to this finding, a study conducted by Downing et al. (2020) found that student fear of negative evaluation may be reduced by allowing students to work in groups with other students whom they know, providing a chance for students to talk to their classmate before sharing with the class and framing errors as part of the learning process.

Thus, a participant which expressed his fear of being criticized by his classmates for presenting his performance in class, saying that,

“Nabalaka ko basin, hmm... sayop akong pagconstruct og pagspell sa word, og pagstorya sa English. Nabalaka sab ko kay kailangan man siya ipresent, ahm... sa kadaghanan, unya basin katawan or ijudge sa akong classmate akong gibuhat.” [I'm worried that maybe I'm constructing and spelling the word wrong and talking in English. I'm also worried because I have to present him to the majority, and then maybe my classmate will judge what I did.”]- I5, L17-20

Furthermore, the learners' perceptions of fear of performing in English in class presentations offered reasons. This is in line with the study by Rafek et al. (2018), which found that learners will lack confidence and not be able to perform well in class if they feel that they are being watched and observed.

Table 3.3 shows the level of secondary language classroom anxiety of the participants in terms of test anxiety.

Table 3.3

Level of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety Among Grade 7 Students in Terms of Test Anxiety

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
2. I don't worry about making mistakes in language class.	3.65	Agree	Anxious
8. I am usually at ease (comfortable) during tests in my language class.	3.15	Agree	Anxious
10. I worry about the consequences of failing my language class.	3.89	Agree	Anxious
19. I am afraid that my language teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make.	3.70	Neutral	Mildly Anxious
21. The more I study for a language test, the more confused I get.	3.73	Agree	Anxious
Average	3.62	Agree	Anxious

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Neutral, 3.50-4.49-Agree, 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree

As gleaned from the table 3.3, it can be noted that the highest weighted mean is 3.89, which can be interpreted as anxious. This shows that learners are worried if they fail in their language class. This also implies that learners have the fear of failing and are stressed about having their oral or written test in English class. While, the lowest weighted mean is 3.15, which is interpreted as mildly anxious. This shows that some students are comfortable during tests in language class. The overall weighted mean of the extent of language anxiety in terms of test anxiety is 3.62, which can be interpreted as anxious. This implies that learners are anxious about their written and oral tests in their language class.

Similarly, Lestari (2020) showed that the learners experienced anxious feelings when they wanted to use the target language that were affected by factors such as fear of the test, dread of negative assessment, and English communication apprehension. In addition, this was supported by Budiman, Ngadiso, and Suparno (2018) who enumerated fear of examinations and worry about communicating as the most anxious factors for language learners.

In contrast, Yasuda and Nabei (2018) stated that every time students exert effort in studying and prepare in advance, they develop a feeling of confidence in their abilities where the fear of negative evaluation is lessened. Thus, it is imperative for teachers to create a welcoming, relaxed, and supportive English language classroom (Gatcho & Hajan, 2019).

However, 7th participant who shared his struggles in terms of overthinking the outcome of the performance by experiencing the fear to perform in front speaking English by saying that,

“Mabalaka ko kay ahh... basin dili ko performing well sa among English, kay kailangan man siya iperform unya... ahm...sa kadaghanan, tas mahadlok man gyud ko mo storya og English. Tas mahaldok sab ko kung gamay rako og grades. [I'm worried because I might not be performing well in our English and I have to perform it in front of people, but I'm really worried about speaking in English. I am also very afraid that I will receive low grades.]”- 17, L54-57

Moreover, the learners’ perceptions of being worried about having low grades in the English language in class presentations offered reasons. This is in line with the study by Paul Sun & Jun Zhang (2022), which found that when compared to other courses, oral learners have a higher level of anxiety. Anxiety over speaking in public is a typical problem among English language students.

Table 3.4 shows the level of secondary language classroom anxiety of the participants in terms of anxiety of English classes.

Table 3.4
Level of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety Among Grade 7 Students in Terms of Anxiety of English Classes

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4. It frightens me when I don't understand what the teacher is saying in English.	3.58	Agree	Anxious
5. I wouldn't bother me at all to take more English language classes.	3.59	Agree	Anxious
6. During language class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the course.	3.64	Agree	Anxious
11. I don't understand why some people get so upset over language classes.	3.66	Agree	Anxious
12. In language class, I can get so nervous that I forgot things I know.	3.72	Agree	Anxious
16. Even if I am well prepared for language class, I feel anxious about it.	3.68	Agree	Anxious
17. I often feel like not going to my language class.	3.61	Agree	Anxious
22. I don't feel pressure to prepare very well for language class.	3.62	Agree	Anxious
26. I feel more tense and nervous in my language class than in my other class.	3.67	Agree	Anxious
28. When I'm on my way to language class, I feel very confident and relaxed.	3.62	Agree	Anxious
30. I feel overwhelmed by the number of rules you have to learn to speak the English language.	3.66	Agree	Anxious
Average	3.64	Agree	Anxious

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Neutral, 3.50-4.49-Agree, 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree

This table 3.4 shows that the highest weighted mean is 3.72, which is interpreted as anxious. This implies that learners are anxious towards the language class, and they tend to forget the things they know due to nervousness. However, the lowest weighted mean is 3.58, which is interpreted as anxious. This

means that learners are anxious if they don't understand what the teacher is saying during their English class.

The overall weighted mean of the extent of language anxiety in terms of anxiety in English classes is 3.62, which can be interpreted as anxious. This implies that learners are anxious about dealing with activities or performances in language class. Furthermore, when teachers are able to motivate and inspire students, they can also influence students' abilities to learn English (Indriani, 2020). Similarly, Ran et al., (2022), which noted that negative emotions like worry, fear, tension, and wrath, in particular, might jeopardize a learner's ideal learning potential and significantly diminish their language learning ability.

On the contrary, Kurniawan (2016) revealed that practicing is a strategy that can be implemented by students to solve their problems in anxiety in oral presentation. The study also found ways students deal with their anxiety in presentation are preparation before presentation, relaxation, positive thinking, peer seeking and focus. Similarly, Blegur et al. (2023) stated that consistent practice of oral presentation skills can improve the precision of the information conveyed, the effectiveness of communication and the articulation of speech.

This finding is also supported by the participant who shared his experiences of overthinking the possible outcome of the performance, saying that,

“Grabi akong kakulba og kahadlok, basin dili nako siya ma-deliver og tarong akong pagrecite sa poetry. Basin ahm... masayop ko pag pronounce sa word sa English. Unya kanang... ma-mental block ko kay nakalimot sa akong lines. [I was very nervous and afraid that I might not be able to deliver my poetry correctly. I might mispronounce the word in English. Then I get a mental block because I forget my lines]”- I3, L47-49

The utterances of the participant shows that it is not uncommon to feel uncertain and anxious, especially when you are unsure about how to pronounce a word correctly. This uncertainty can lead to overthinking, which further fuels the fear of speaking in public. However, it is important to remember that making mistakes is a natural part of learning and growth.

Moreover, the learners' insights are to cope with anxiety during oral activities in language class. This observation highlights the importance of preparation, a recurring theme in other studies that have highlighted the effectiveness of rehearsal, the use of visual aids, and focusing on content as effective coping strategies (Tóth, 2019; Kembaren et al., 2022).

In addition, this is supported by the theory of Stephen Krashen, which is the Affective Filter Hypothesis, which states that a lack of motivation, poor levels of self-confidence, and chronic anxiety can "increase" the affective filter and

create a "mental block" that restricts the utilization of understandable input for the purpose of acquisition. The result shows that the 3rd informant experiences mental blocks during the oral presentation in their English class.

Research Question 4. Language Anxiety Experienced During Class Oral Presentations When Group According to Profile

Table 4 shows the significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when group according to profile.

Table 4.1

Significant Difference in Language Anxiety Experienced During Class Oral Presentations Between Male and Female Participants

Language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations	Sex	Mean	SD	p-value	Remark
Communication Apprehension	Male	4.01	1.18	0.000	Significant
	Female	3.07	1.40		
Fear of Negative Evaluation	Male	4.03	0.87	0.001	Significant
	Female	3.26	1.33		
Test Anxiety	Male	3.95	0.91	0.002	Significant
	Female	3.22	1.32		
Anxiety of English Classes	Male	3.98	0.94	0.011	Significant
	Female	3.22	1.37		

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance using independent sample t-test.*

As shown in the table 4.1, there are four factors experienced by learners in dealing with language anxiety in class oral presentations, along with the learner's sex. It shows that males had a higher mean score of 4.01 compared to females, indicating that males, on average, experienced higher levels of communication apprehension during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. In dealing with fear of negative evaluation, the result shows that males had a higher mean score of 4.03 compared to females, indicating that males, on average, experienced higher levels of fear of negative evaluation during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.001.

In dealing with the test anxiety, the result shows that males had a higher mean score of 3.95 compared to females, indicating that males, on average, experienced higher levels of test anxiety during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.002. The result shows that the anxiety in English classes indicates that males had a higher mean score of 3.98 compared to females, indicating that males, on average, experienced higher levels of anxiety related to English classes during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.011.

Thus, the results show that males tend to experience higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations compared to females, as indicated by their higher mean scores across all categories. This finding is

supported by Elaldi (2016) stated that males are more anxious than females in foreign language classes. Studies have indicated that male students may experience higher levels of anxiety in language classrooms (Taylor et al., 2020).

In contrast, Gerencheal (2016), it was found that females had higher anxiety levels in their English classes than their counterparts' males. On the other hand, Sahid et al. (2018) reported in their study that a female participant repeatedly touched her head using both hands when she felt anxious during a seminar presentation.

Table 4.2 shows the significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations and the type of school graduated during their sixth-grade level, which are public and private schools.

Table 4.2
Significant Difference in Language Anxiety Experienced During Class Oral Presentations and the Type of School Graduated of Participants

Language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations	Type of School Graduated	Mean	SD	p-value	Remark
Communication Apprehension	Public	4.07	1.07	0.000	Significant
	Private	2.35	1.26		
Fear of Negative Evaluation	Public	4.09	0.80	0.000	Significant
	Private	2.64	1.30		
Test Anxiety	Public	4.03	0.86	0.000	Significant
	Private	2.58	1.21		
Anxiety of English Classes	Public	4.06	0.88	0.000	Significant
	Private	2.56	1.26		

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance using independent sample t-test.*

The table 4.2 shows that there are four factors experienced by learners in dealing with language anxiety in class oral presentations, along with the learner's type of school graduated in their sixth-grade level. It displays that public school had a higher mean score of 4.07 with a standard deviation of 1.07, compared to private school, indicating that public school, on average, experienced higher levels of communication apprehension during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. In dealing with the fear of negative evaluation, it shows that public school had a higher mean score of 4.09 with a standard deviation of 0.80, compared to private school, indicating that public school, on average, experienced higher levels of fear of negative evaluation during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000.

However, the test anxiety shows that public school had a higher mean score of 4.03 with a standard deviation of 0.86, compared to private school, indicating that public school, on average, experienced higher levels of test anxiety during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. On the other hand, the anxiety of English classes results shows that public school had a higher mean score of 4.06 with a standard deviation of

0.88, compared to private school, indicating that public school, on average, experienced higher levels of anxiety of English classes during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. Furthermore, the results show that public school tend to experience higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations compared to private school, as indicated by their higher mean scores across all categories.

However, a study conducted by Khoshsima and Hashemi Toroujeni (2017) found that students attending private schools outperformed those who attended state schools in speaking performance. Moreover, Elaldı (2016) stated that males are more anxious than females in foreign language classes. Studies have indicated that male students may experience higher levels of anxiety in language classrooms (Taylor et al., 2020).

In contrast, a study conducted by Mestan's (2017) showed that in regard to anxiety manifesting itself differently for students at the secondary level, speaking anxiety increases according the student's grade, so for those who have reached their secondary level, they are likely experiencing years of inner speaking anxiety, which then makes it more difficult for students to speak in front of others.

Table 4.3 shows the significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations and the preferred modes of communication of the participants, which are verbal, nonverbal, written, visual, and audio.

Table 4.3

Significant Difference in Language Anxiety Experienced During Class Oral Presentations and Preferred Mode of Communication of the Participants

Language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations	Mode of Communication	Mean	SD	p-value	Remark
Communication Apprehension	Verbal	4.88	1.41	0.000	Significant
	Written	4.68	0.45		
	Audio	3.98	0.96		
	Visual	4.36	0.31		
	Non-verbal	2.78	1.37		
Fear of Negative Evaluation	Verbal	4.64	0.18	0.000	Significant
	Written	3.08	1.33		
	Audio	3.99	0.81		
	Visual	4.35	0.36		
	Non-verbal	4.30	0.42		
Test Anxiety	Verbal	3.05	1.29	0.000	Significant
	Written	4.64	0.17		
	Audio	3.80	0.96		
	Visual	4.31	0.33		
	Non-verbal	4.33	0.58		
Anxiety of English Classes	Verbal	4.71	0.22	0.000	Significant
	Written	4.00	0.89		
	Audio	2.96	1.33		
	Visual	4.34	0.28		
	Non-verbal	4.46	0.29		

*Tested at 0.05 level of significance using ANOVA

As gleaned from the table 4.3, it can be noted that there are four factors of language anxiety in class oral presentations such as: communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and anxiety of English

classes. Also, it shows the types of preferred mode of communication which are the verbal, nonverbal, written, visual, and audio communication. The results shows that verbal communication had a higher mean score of 4.88 with a standard deviation of 1.41, indicating that verbal communication, on average, experienced higher levels of communication apprehension during class oral presentations. While, the audio communication shows as the lower weighted mean score of 3.98 with a standard deviation of 0.96, indicating that audio communication, on average, experienced lower levels of communication apprehension during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. In dealing with the fear of negative evaluation it shows that the verbal communication is the higher weighted mean score of 4.64 with a standard deviation of 0.18, indicating that verbal communication, on average, experienced higher levels of fear of negative evaluation during class oral presentations. Then the written communication shows the lower weighted mean score of 3.08 with a standard deviation of 1.33, indicating that written communication, on average, experienced lower levels of fear of negative evaluation during class oral presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000.

Meanwhile, the test anxiety shows that written communication had a higher weighted mean score of 4.64 with a standard deviation of 0.17, indicating that written communication, on average, experienced higher levels of test anxiety during class presentations. On the other hand, the verbal communication had a lower mean score of 3.05 with a standard deviation of 1.29, indicating that verbal communication, on average, experienced lower levels of verbal communication during class presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. Furthermore, for the anxiety of English classes shows that verbal communication had a higher weighted mean score of 4.71 with a standard deviation of 0.22, indicating that verbal communication, on average, experienced higher levels of anxiety of English classes during class oral presentations. However, audio communication shows lower weighted mean score of 2.96 with a standard deviation of 1.33, indicating that audio communication, on average, experienced lower levels of audio communication during class presentations. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.000. Thus, the results shows that verbal communication tend to experience higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations as indicated by their higher mean scores across all categories.

On the contrary, Guo et al., (2018) revealed that students with high speech anxiety would prefer those subjects where speaking skills are not the focus when given the option to choose. Oral presentations rely on effective communication, which includes elements such as clear pronunciation, intonation of voice and projection, all of which significantly affect the overall impact and understanding of the presentation (Chiang et al., 2021; Blegur et al., 2023).

Research Question 5. The Academic Performance of the Students and the Factors of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety

Table 5 shows the significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety.

Table 5

Significant Relationship Between Academic Performance of the Participants and the Factors of Secondary Language Classroom Anxiety

Language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations	Academic Performance		
	Pearson's <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Remark
Communication Apprehension	-0.69	0.000	Significant
Fear of Negative Evaluation	-0.61	0.000	Significant
Test Anxiety	-0.60	0.000	Significant
Anxiety of English Classes	-0.68	0.000	Significant

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's r Correlation*

As presented in the table, the correlation coefficient or Pearson's *r* between communication apprehension and academic performance is -0.69, which indicates a strong negative correlation. The *p*-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. This means that as communication apprehension increases, academic performance tends to decrease. Also, the correlation coefficient between fear of negative evaluation and academic performance is -0.61, indicating a strong negative correlation. As fear of negative evaluation increases, academic performance tends to decrease. The *p*-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. Then, the correlation coefficient between test anxiety and academic performance is -0.60, indicating a strong negative correlation. As test anxiety increases, academic performance tends to decrease. The *p*-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. Finally, the correlation coefficient between anxiety in English classes and academic performance is -0.68, indicating a strong negative correlation. The *p*-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. This means that as anxiety related to English classes increases, academic performance tends to decrease. Overall, these results suggest that higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations are associated with lower academic performance. Students who experience more anxiety in these situations are likely to perform less well academically.

This finding is supported by Arjanggih, et al. (2016) reported in their study that the lower the students' social anxiety, the more students' academic adjustment will be. Similarly, Sung et al. (2016) found that for low-achieving pupil's greater levels of test anxiety was found to be positively related to achievement, while for high-achieving pupils the relationship was negative. Moreover, this finding is

supported by Anwar (2017) revealed that the students' English academic achievement was categorized as failed or can be said poor could be because the respondents had difficulties in English based on their overall English class grade. El-Omari (2016) stated that the factors could explain the poor achievement of students are that some learners would skip the English class or hate the English teacher. Thus, Tujuba and Davidson (2017) explained that one of the factors that caused this poor achievement was that the time to practice English is very short, and the less motivation of teachers to support students in learning English.

In contrast, Goh (2017) emphasized the importance of normalizing mistakes and creating a positive and encouraging atmosphere where students feel comfortable taking risks when speaking English. Encouraging positive reinforcement also involves acknowledging that English is not the students' primary language (Inada, 2021). Moreover, Aguirre and Legaspi (2020) stated that older learners are more capable of performing well in academics than the younger ones. Furthermore, a study conducted by Fujii (2017) introduced two (2) student-oriented strategies: (1) cooperation with others & (2) building confidence; and another two (2) teacher-oriented strategies, respectively: (1) assistance from the teacher & (2) less-stressful teaching methods.

In addition, this finding is supported by the theory of Albert Bandura, which is the Social Cognitive Theory, which is focused on how individuals operate cognitively based on their social experiences and how these cognitions then influence behavior and development. It explains how individuals acquire and maintain certain behavioral patterns. That person's behavior can be caused by personal, behavioral, and environmental influences. It is also used to analyze how symbolic communication influences human thought, effects, and action. Lastly, it implies that for negative and positive learning to occur, a learner should have positive characteristics, exhibit appropriate behavior, and stay in a supportive environment; if not, it leads to negativity, which leads to shame and anxiety. Similarly, Mahbub and Hadina (2021) stated that a complex interrelationship between psychological, linguistic, social, and educational factors that contribute to this widespread problem. Thus, this emphasized the importance of observational learning, social interaction, and cognitive processes in understanding and changing behavior. This affects their behavior, environment, and themselves through learning and speaking the language. As presented in the table 5, the correlation coefficient or Pearson's r between communication apprehension and academic performance is -0.69 , which indicates a strong negative correlation. The p -value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. This means that as communication apprehension increases, academic performance tends to decrease. Also, the correlation coefficient between fear of negative evaluation and academic performance is -0.61 , indicating a strong negative correlation. As fear of negative evaluation increases, academic performance tends to decrease. The p -value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. Then, the correlation coefficient between test anxiety and academic performance is -0.60 , indicating a strong negative correlation. As test anxiety increases, academic

performance tends to decrease. The p-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. Finally, the correlation coefficient between anxiety in English classes and academic performance is -0.68, indicating a strong negative correlation. The p-value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant. This means that as anxiety related to English classes increases, academic performance tends to decrease. Overall, these results suggest that higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations are associated with lower academic performance. Students who experience more anxiety in these situations are likely to perform less well academically.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Arjanggih, et al. (2016) reported in their study that the lower the students' social anxiety, the more students' academic adjustment will be. Moreover, this finding is supported by Anwar (2017) revealed that the students' English academic achievement was categorized as failed or can be said poor could be because the respondents had difficulties in English based on their overall English class grade.

In contrast, Aguirre and Legaspi (2020) stated that older learners are more capable of performing well in academics than the younger ones. Furthermore, a study conducted by Fujii (2017) introduced two (2) student-oriented strategies: (1) cooperation with others & (2) building confidence; and another two (2) teacher-oriented strategies, respectively: (1) assistance from the teacher & (2) less-stressful teaching methods.

Research Question 6. The Participants Experiences of English Language Anxiety in Class Oral Presentations

Table 6 shows the participants experiences of English language anxiety in class oral presentations that show the themes based on the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) analysis. Then, the data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Seven themes emerged, namely: (1) lack of confidence to speak English during oral recitations, (2) afraid of being criticized, (3) uncontrollable fear of performing, (4) feeling worried to have low grades, (5) Intimidated by other's superior performance, (6) overthinking about the possible outputs of performance, and (7) ways to cope with anxiety in English class performance.

Theme 1: Lack of Confidence to Speak English During Oral Recitations

Theme 2: Afraid of Being Criticized

Theme 3: Uncontrollable Fear of Performing

Theme 4: Feeling Worried to Have Low Grades

Theme 5: Intimidated by Other's Superior Performance

Theme 6: Overthinking about the Possible Outputs of Performance

Theme 7: Ways to Cope with Anxiety in English Class Performance

Furthermore, the results shows that participants experience higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations. This finding is similar to the result of Navaz and Banu (2019) revealed that students feel most anxious during oral activities such as test and presentations, and half of the respondents feel anxious “sometimes” in English as a second language (ESL) class. They may face problems during oral presentations, including difficulties to express their thoughts, which may lead to mumbling (Soomro et al., 2019). This finding is supported by Ka-kan-dee and Al-Shaibani (2018) showed that most respondents have the highest level of anxiety during oral presentations and the interview reveals that most of them dislike oral presentations. Feeling of anxiety is reported very commonly because they express student negative emotional reaction towards English language learning such as tension, nervousness and worries and many other problems (Bhatti, 2016).

This finding is contrary to the study of Kurniawan (2016) found that practicing is a strategy that can be implemented by students to solve their problems in anxiety in oral presentation. This observation highlights the importance of preparation, a recurring theme in other studies that have highlighted the effectiveness of rehearsal, the use of visual aids, and focusing on content as effective coping strategies (Tóth, 2019; Kembaren et al., 2022). Moreover, Seven (2020) stated that motivation is a very significant and effective element in the realm of learning a language. Students' motivation could also have a positive impact on their achievement scores in English (Dilshad et al., 2019).

In addition, this finding is supported by the theory of Edward Deci and Richard Ryan, which is the Self-determination Theory, which is an empirically derived theory of human motivation and personality in social contexts that differentiates motivation in terms of being autonomous and controlled. This theory can be incorporated into teaching through various strategies, such as supporting autonomy, encouraging relatedness, and cultivating competence. In this case, individuals are more likely to be intrinsically motivated when their basic psychological needs are met. In the context of language anxiety, fostering intrinsic motivation can be crucial for overcoming challenges.

Research Question 7. Proposed Intervention Program

The proposed intervention program for language anxiety is to enhance students' language learning experiences, improve their language proficiency, and promote their overall well-being and academic success. Based on the findings of this study, which shows that there is a significant relationship between academic performance of the students and the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety, the intervention program is designed to equip students with the skills and strategies they need to manage their anxiety effectively, allowing them to communicate more confidently and proficiently in English.

This program is correlated to the concept of critical language pedagogy in language teaching which is a standpoint in language curriculum theory and

instructional practice that supports and advances teaching and the study of languages. The reason for implementing this particular pedagogy in educational practices lies in the modernization of hierarchical structures not only in education but also in society (Sarani, Najjarbaghseyah, & Vaezi, 2019). Hence, the success of language learning lies in the students' personal involvement with covered issues and the benefits they can personally draw from it (Barboni, 2022).

PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM

- I. **Program Title:** Language Confidence: Overcoming Language Anxiety
- II. **Program Description:** This intervention program is designed by the researcher based on the findings of the study English Language Anxiety in Class Oral Presentation of Grade 7 students in the New Normal.
- III. **Program Objectives:**
 - The intervention program is based on the outcomes of the study English Language Anxiety in Class Oral Presentation of Grade 7 Students in the New Normal. Where if, the result of the test is required immediate attention, the researchers will design an assessment program to enhance students in overcoming language anxiety.
 - This aims to create a supportive and engaging environment where students can develop their language skills while effectively managing their anxiety. By addressing both the psychological and educational aspects of language learning, the program strives to empower students to become more confident and proficient language learners.
- IV. **Target Audience:** Student experiencing anxiety related to learning the English language in Junior High School.
- V. **Duration:** 9 weeks (1-2 session per week)
- VI. **Scheme Implementation:**

The program is divided into three (3) phases. Phase I in the Pre-Intervention Phase wherein the design program will be endorsed to the school administrators for consideration and implementation. After that, teacher and parents will be oriented to help students boost confidence addressing language anxiety. Phase 2 is the intervention phase wherein the design program is put into action. Phase 3 is the Post intervention wherein the administrators and teachers' make an assessment plan to check and evaluate student's progress.
- VII. **Key Components:**
 - **Qualified Facilitators:** Educators, psychologist, and counselors experienced in teaching languages and handling anxiety.
 - **Safe and Supportive Environment:** A non-judgmental space wherein mistakes are viewed as part of the learning process.
 - **Regular Feedback:** Providing constructive feedback to help students track their progress and areas for improvement.
 - **Customized Content:** Tailoring materials to suit the proficiency level and interests or the group.

Figure 3. Phases of the Proposed Scheme

Phase I. Pre-Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endorsement of the designed intervention program to the school administrators. • Teachers and parents' orientation for students' progress in dealing with coping language anxiety. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Request for a meeting with the school administrators. ➤ Endorsement of the proposed intervention program. ➤ Teachers having an orientation, seminars, workshop, psychological approaches, mental wellness, authentic assessments, and lack session in dealing with students experiencing language anxiety and how to help them overcome language anxiety and boost confidence to learn a new language. ➤ To educate parents about the importance of their role in supporting their children's confidence and addressing language anxiety. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ To inform and orient the school administrators with the proposed intervention program. ➤ To educate teachers, equip them with strategies and techniques on the importance of addressing language anxiety and its impact on students' confidence and performance. ➤ To establish a partnership between parents and teachers in addressing language anxiety, fostering open communication, and supporting students' confidence-building efforts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ School Administrators ➤ Researcher ➤ Coordinators ➤ Teachers ➤ Parents 	None	Plan and program of activities

Phase II. During Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 2	<p>Introduction and Assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers Orientation dealing language anxiety Understanding Language Anxiety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to the program, ice-breaking activities, and setting personal goals for students. Assessing individual levels of language anxiety through surveys or questionnaires. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presenting and assessing varied activities for language anxiety involves addressing the fear and discomfort students may feel while learning a new language. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers Administrators Guidance Counselor/ Guidance Advocate Keynote Speaker (Educational Expert or Psychologist) Students 	₱ 7,000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certificate Attendance Form Printed Surveys or questionnaire
Week 3-4	<p>Coping Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sessions on Cognitive-Behavioral Techniques Building Confidence Relaxation and Breathing Exercises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educating students about the nature of anxiety and teaching cognitive-behavioral strategies to manage anxious thoughts related to language learning. Guided sessions to help students manage physical symptoms of anxiety. 	<p>To enhance students with practical skills grounded in cognitive-behavioral techniques, fostering an environment of self-efficacy and resilience in the face of mental health challenges.</p> <p>The structured sessions facilitate a comprehensive learning experience, promoting the integration of cognitive-behavioral techniques (CBT) into participants' daily lives for sustained mental well-being.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers Administrators Guidance Counselor/ Guidance Advocate Keynote Speaker (Educational Expert or Psychologist) Students 	₱ 7,000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certificate Attendance Form Worksheet Audiovisual materials
Week 5	<p>Skill Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective Communication Skills Workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities focused on building basic communication skills in the target language, such as simple 	<p>To help students develop with a comprehensive set of communication skills and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers Administrators Keynote Speaker (English Educators) Students 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certificate Attendance Form Audiovisual materials

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pronunciation Practice • Overcoming Fear of Mistakes 	<p>dialogues, role-playing, and group discussions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sessions to practice and improve pronunciation, reducing self-consciousness about speaking. 	<p>pronunciation practice in recognizing the pivotal role of effective communication that plays in personal and professional success.</p>			
Week 6	<p>Interactive and Immersive Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Language Games and Competitions ➤ Cultural Immersion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Engaging activities like language games, quizzes, and friendly competitions to create a fun and less stressful learning environment. ➤ Incorporating cultural aspects related to the language, including music, films, and cuisine, to build a deeper connection and interest in the language. 	<p>It recognizes the vital role that cultural setting plays in language acquisition. By combining English language instruction with cultural immersion and experiential learning, participants can more effectively acquire language skills while gaining a nuanced understanding of the cultures where the language is spoken.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Teachers ➤ Administrators ➤ Keynote Speaker (English Educators) ➤ Students 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Attendance Form
Week 7	<p>Peer Support and Group Dynamics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Peer Feedback Sessions ➤ Group Activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Creating opportunities for students to give and receive constructive feedback in a supportive environment. ➤ Encouraging collaboration on small projects related to the target language. 	<p>This is designed to leverage the power of collaborative learning and peer interaction to enhance English language proficiency. By engaging in group projects and structured peer feedback, participants can not only refine their language skills but also develop key soft skills such as teamwork, communication, and critical thinking.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ English Teachers ➤ Students 	None	Attendance Group Projects

<p>Week 8</p>	<p>Evaluation and Future Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Progress Assessment ➤ Strategic Learning Plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Re-assessing language anxiety levels and discussing improvements or changes in feelings towards language learning. ➤ Guiding teachers to set up a future strategic learning plan to develop students in overcoming language anxiety and builds language confidence. 	<p>This aims to create a positive and effective evaluation, assessment, and learning plans. It recognizes the unique challenges faced by each learner and seeks to empower them with the skills and confidence needed to overcome language anxiety and achieve proficiency.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Administrators ➤ Teachers 	<p>None</p>	<p>Evaluation Form Learning Plans Assessments</p>
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Phase III. Post Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 9	Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Pre and post intervention assessments to measure changes in language anxiety levels. ➤ Regular monitoring of student's progress. ➤ Collecting feedback from students at the end of the program to evaluate its effectiveness and areas for improvement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Establishing a structured assessment plan, the program can ensure that the approaches and strategies used are directly addressing these challenges. ➤ Continuous monitoring and evaluation allow for the adaptation of methods to best suit the evolving needs of learners, ultimately leading to more effective language acquisition and a positive learning experience. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. School Administrators 2. Researcher 3. Teachers 	None	Assessment Plan

Sources:

Young, D. J. (2016). *An investigation of students' perspectives on anxiety and speaking. Foreign Language Annals*

Bandura, A. (2017). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control. W.H. Freeman*

Gudykunst, W. B. (2019). *Theories in intercultural communication. International and Intercultural Communication Annual*

Brantmeier, C. (2019). *Anxiety about L2 learning in a study abroad context: The role of individual and situational variables*

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to determine the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety and their academic performance in English. This also attempted to identify language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when group according to profile which are the sex, type of school graduated, and preferred mode of communication.

It utilized a convergent parallel mixed-methods research design and an adapted survey questionnaire to gather numerical data on the variables. It employed an interview questionnaire to collect in-depth insights and experiences related to English language anxiety in class oral presentations. The study hypothesized that there is a significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when group according to profile. There is also a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety. There were 143 participants in the study, and they were chosen using stratified random sampling.

The findings of the study revealed that the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex was dominated by males. In terms of the type of school they graduated during their sixth-grade level, it turned out that the majority of the respondents graduated from a public school. Also, in terms of their academic performance, it turned out that the most students garnered as satisfactory. For the preferred mode of communication of the participants, it turned out that the majority's mode of communication was verbal communication.

In terms of the level factors of secondary language classroom anxiety among Grade 7 students in terms of communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and anxiety of English classes, it turned out that communication apprehension had the highest overall weighted mean of 3.59, and fear of negative evaluation had the highest overall weighted mean of 3.68. While, in terms of the test anxiety, the highest overall weighted mean was 3.62, and in terms of anxiety in English class, the highest possible overall weighted mean was 3.64. In terms of the language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when grouped according to profile, it turned out that males tend to experience higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations compared to females, as indicated by their higher mean scores across all categories.

Due to the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety and their academic performance in English, it turned out that higher levels of language anxiety during class oral presentations are associated with lower academic performance. Thus, academic performance is likely to be affected by students who feel more anxious in these situations. This highlights that students who perform poorly in English classes have higher levels of anxiety, which may lead to an increase in anxiety on their part.

Conclusions

The majority of the respondents are male; most of them graduated from public school during their sixth grade; and most of the respondents preferred verbal communication; their academic performance shows that participants grades indicated as satisfactory.

There is a significant level of secondary language classroom anxiety among Grade 7 students in terms of communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and anxiety in English classes. There is a significant difference in language anxiety experienced during class oral presentations when grouped according to profile. There is a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and the factors of secondary language classroom anxiety.

Based on the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) analysis shows that learners experiences anxiety during class oral presentations. Then, seven themes emerged, namely: (1) lack of confidence to speak English during oral recitations, (2) afraid of being criticized, (3) uncontrollable fear of performing, (4) feeling worried to have low grades, (5) Intimidated by other's superior performance, (6) overthinking about the possible outputs of performance, and (7) ways to cope with anxiety in English class performance. An educational intervention program will help students enhance their learning experiences, allowing them to focus and participate more effectively in class activities or performances in English classes. Moreover, it can lead to improved academic performance and increased confidence in their language abilities. Therefore, this approach aims to reduce language anxiety and can help students develop essential communication skills, preparing them for future academic and professional challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are drawn.

1. The teachers may provide clear expectations for oral presentations and offer guidance on how students can improve their speaking skills; provide ample opportunities for students to practice speaking in low-pressure settings, such as small group discussions or pair work; and offer constructive feedback on students' speaking skills, focusing on areas for improvement while also acknowledging their strengths.
2. The school may create an established and dedicated comprehensive support system within the school to identify and assist students facing language anxiety. It may present an orientation that is led by the guidance counselor, providing access to counseling services or support groups for students to address their anxieties and build confidence.
3. The school administrators may provide professional development by organizing seminars, workshops, nationwide in-depth orientation on dealing with language assessment anxiety for curriculum designers or training sessions for teachers to enhance their understanding of language anxiety and equip them with strategies to support students.

4. The school may create supportive policies that promote a supportive environment for students facing language anxiety, such as allowing flexible assessment methods or providing additional support resources. Also, the school may have their own guidance counselors in helping students facing language anxiety to overcome their fears and succeed academically. By this, the students may learn coping strategies, such as relaxation techniques and positive self-talk, to help them manage their anxiety.
5. There may be teacher-parent collaboration, parental support for students, and peer support and collaboration with others. It would be good practice for the teachers, parents, and students to work hand in hand to strive to understand the language anxiety and provide support for students facing this experience. This can include listening to their concerns, offering reassurance, and providing strategies to cope with anxiety.
6. The school may develop a tailored intervention program to effectively support students experiencing language anxiety during class oral presentations. This program should encompass various strategies aimed at building students' confidence and reducing anxiety levels.
7. Researchers in the field of education may replicate this study, as it may help them succeed in investigating language anxiety in class oral presentations like focusing on the five macro skills which are the reading, writing, speaking, listening, and viewing. They may also come up with their own study, focusing on evidence-based strategies and insights that can inform effective interventions to support students in managing language anxiety during oral presentations.
8. This may inform teachers to recognize the value of students' second language (L2) in mitigating language anxiety. Pedagogies should integrate opportunities for students to use their L2 alongside English, fostering a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. By valuing and incorporating students' second language (L2) in the classroom, it can greatly contribute to reducing language anxiety and promoting a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study subscribed to the principles of voluntary participation in research, implying that the respondents might withdraw from this research at any time. Informed consent, which means that the participants must at all times be fully informed about the research process and purposes, and must give consent to their participation in this research. Safety and participation, put differently, means that the researchers will make sure that participants are not placed at risk or harm of any kind. Privacy, meaning that the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants should be protected at all times. And trust, which implies that the participants will not be subjected to any acts of deception or betrayal in this research process or its published outcomes and have the right to know the conclusion of this study.

Likewise, the researchers understand what plagiarism entails and is aware of the school's policy in this regard. We undertake not to make use of another person's previous work without acknowledgement or to submit it as my own.

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REFERENCES

- Abrar, M., Failasofah, Fajaryani, & N., M. (2016). EFL student teachers' Speaking Anxiety: The case in one English teacher education program. *IJEE (Indonesian Journal of English Education)*, 3(1), 60-75. doi:10.15408/ijee. v3i1.3619.
- Abu-Rabia, S. (2014). Teachers' role, learners' gender differences, and FL anxiety among seventh-grade students Studying English as a FL. *Educational Psychology*, 24 (5), 711-721

- Afrianti, D., & Afna, M. (2020). Who is more anxious in learning a foreign language: males or females? *INSPIRA: Indonesian Journal of Psychological Research*, 1(2), 49-56.
<https://doi.org/10.32505/inspira.v1i2.2877>
- Aguirre, P., & Legaspi, C. (2020). Predictors of academic performance of public elementary school learners. *Philippine Social Science Journal*
- Arabai, F. (2014). A model of foreign language anxiety in the Saudi EFL context. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*, 7(7), 82-101
- Alzamil, J. (2021). Listening Skills: Important but Difficult to Learn. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)* Volume 12. Number3 September 2021, Available at
 SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3952957> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3952957>
- American Psychological Association, 2015. Available from
www.apa.org/topics/anxiety/
- Anwar, M. (2017). ESL/EFL learners' poor performance in English: The factors. *Journal of Asian and African Social Science and Humanities*, 3, 18–26.
- Anwari, Ahmad (2019), 'Investigating the causes and negative effects of English language speaking anxiety: A Case Study among EFL Learners at Kandahar University', *American International Journal of Education and Linguistics Research*, 2.2, 10–21
- Arjanggi, R. – Kusumaningsih, L. P. S. 2016. The correlation between social anxiety and academic adjustment among freshmen. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 219 (2016), pp. 104-107.
- Atas, M. (2015). The reduction of speaking anxiety in EFL learners through drama techniques. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 961–969.
- Aydin, S. (2007, November 30). Eric - Ed512266 - An Investigation on The Language Anxiety and Fear of Negative Evaluation Among Turkish EFL Learners, Online Submission, 2008. Eric
- Bandura, A. (2000). Self-efficacy: The foundation of agency. *Control of Human Behavior, Mental Processes, and Consciousness: Essays in Honor of the 60th Birthday of August Flammer*. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2000-08381-002>
- Bandura, A. (2017). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. W.H. Freeman
- Barboni, S. (2022). Teacher-made critical materials for primary and secondary English language classrooms. In M. Porto (Ed.), *From critical literacy to critical pedagogy in English language teaching* (Vol. 24, pp. 39–67). Singapore: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-5780-1>
- Bhatti, N. (2016). Investigating the perceptions of Pakistani English language learners on language learning anxiety in EFL classroom. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Budiman, Ngadiso, and Suparno. (2018). Exploring English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students' anxiety toward a student-centered learning approach: levels, factors, and strategies to cope with them” in the 1st International Seminar on Language, Literature and Education, *KnE Social Sciences*, pages 64–73. doi: 10.18502/kss.v3i9.2612

- Chang, Y., Brickman, P. (2018). When group work doesn't work: Insights from students. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 17(3), ar52. 10.1187/cbe.17-09-0199
- Chentez, K. J. R., Felicilda Jr, J. V., Felisilda, A. R., & Tabañag, R. E. (2019). Common problems in oral communication skills among high school students. *SMCC Higher Education Research Journal (Teacher Education Journal)*, 1(1), 1-1.
- Chiang, Y. C., Hsiang-Chun, L. E. E., Tsung-Lan, C. H. U., Wu, C. L., & Hsiao, Y. C. (2021). Development and psychometric testing of an oral presentation scale for nursing students. *Research Square*. <https://assets.researchsquare.com/files/rs-275523/v1/0e68f4e4-7d56-4e2e-a93e-653c7eade6a7.pdf?c=1631878388>
- Don, M. A. M., Rosli, M. R., Senin, M. S. M., & Ahmad, M. F. (2022). Exploring social presence theory in the online classroom: The case for online presence. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(1), 26-40. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v12-i1/11440>
- Downing, V. R., Cooper, K. M., Cala, J. M., Gin, L. E., Brownell, S. E. (2020). Fear of negative evaluation and student anxiety in community college active-learning science courses. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 19(2), ar20. 10.1187/cbe.19-09-0186
- Dykstra Steinbrenner, J. R., & Watson, L. R. (2015). Student engagement in the classroom: The impact of classroom, teacher, and student factors. *Journal of Autism and developmental Disorders*, 45, 2392-2410.
- Elaldi, S. (2016). Foreign language anxiety of students studying English Language and Literature: A sample from Turkey. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 11(6), 219-228.
- Erkan, A. (2019). Impact of using technology on teacher-student communication/interaction: Improve students learning. *World Journal of Education*, 9(4), 30-40.
- Fadlan, A. (2020). Factors causing language anxiety of EFL students in classroom presentation. *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 3(2), 219–230. <https://doi.org/10.34050/els-jish.v3i2.9718>
- Fajri, S. N. (2019). Students' Anxiety in Classroom Presentation At English Education Department of UIN Sulthan Thaha Saifuddin Jambi. *English Education Department of UIN Sulthan Thaha Saifuddin Jambi*.
- Fadlan, A. (2020). Factors causing language anxiety of EFL students in classroom presentation. *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 3(2), 219–230. <https://doi.org/10.34050/els-jish.v3i2.9718>
- Fadlan, A. (2020). Factors causing language anxiety of EFL students in classroom presentation. *ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 3(2), 219–230. <https://doi.org/10.34050/els-jish.v3i2.9718>
- Gatcho, A & Hajan, B. (2019). What is so scary about learning English? Investigating language anxiety among Filipino college students. *Journal of English Education*, 8(2), 127–143. doi: 10.24127/pj.v8i2.2221
- Gerencheal, B. (2016). Gender differences in foreign language anxiety at an Ethiopian university: Mizan-Tepi University Third Year English Major Students in Focus. *African Journal of Education and Practice*.

- Goh, C. (2017). Research into practice: Scaffolding learning processes to improve speaking performance. *Language Teaching*, 50 (2), 247-260. doi:10.1017/S0261444816000483
- Google. (2022). Google maps. Retrieved March 5, 2022, from <https://www.google.com/maps/@8.9479092,125.5428007,325m/data=!3m1!1e3?hl=en>
- Grieve, R., Woodley, J., Hunt, S. E., & McKay, A. (2021). Student fears of oral presentations and public speaking in higher education: a qualitative survey. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 45(9), 1281-1293. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877x.2021.1948509>
- Hefel, S. (2022). Impact of student-led discussions on student engagement and involvement (Doctoral dissertation, University of South Carolina).
- Horwitz, E. K. (2001). Language anxiety and achievement. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 21, 112-126
- Horwitz, E. K., et al. (2019). Language anxiety and proficiency in a foreign language. *System*, 85, 8-18.
- Horwitz, E.K., M.B. Horwitz & Cope, J. (1986). Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal* 70. 2, 125–132.
- Inada, T. (2021). Teachers' strategies for decreasing students' anxiety levels to improve their communicative skills. *English Language Teaching*, 14(3), 32. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v14n3p32>
- Indrianty, Septy. (2016). Students' anxiety in speaking English (A case study in one hotel and tourism college in Bandung). *Open Journal Systems*. <https://e-journal.stkipsiliwangi.ac.id/index.php/eltin/article/view/337>
- Jalleh, C. M., Mahfoodh, O. H. A., & Singh, M. K. M. (2021). Oral Communication Apprehension among Japanese EFL International Students in a Language Immersion Program in Malaysia. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(2), 155-178.
- Jin Y. X., Dewaele J. M. (2018). The effect of positive orientation and perceived social support on foreign language classroom anxiety. *System* 74, 149–157. doi: 10.1016/j.system.2018.01.002
- Jordan, K. (2020). Covid-19 school closures in low-and middle-income countries: Emergent perspective on the role of educational technology. *Journal of Learning Development*, 7(3), 399-415.
- Ka-kan-dee, Maleerat, and Ghayth Kamel Shaker Al-Shaibani (2018). Tourism students' oral presentation anxiety: A Case Study, *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 26.T, 231–56 Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330002940_Tourism_Students'_Oral_Presentation_Anxiety_A_Case_Study
- Kembaren, F. R.W., Lubis, S. U., Ramadini, M. (2022). An analysis of STUDENT'S anxiety of oral presentations and public speaking in high education | Kembaren | Vision. *JURNAL TARBIYAH UINSU*. <https://jurnaltarbiyah.uinsu.ac.id/index.php/vision/article/view/1399/0>
- Khan, S. K. & M. a. & S. G. & I. U. K. & N. (2017). Impact of Parents' Occupation on Students Self-Concept at Secondary Level. [ideas.repec.org. https://ideas.repec.org/a/hur/ijarbs/v7y2017i2p46-53.html](https://ideas.repec.org/a/hur/ijarbs/v7y2017i2p46-53.html)

- Khoshshima, H. & Hashemi Toroujeni, S. M. (2017). A comparative study of the government and private sectors' effectiveness in ELT program: A case of Iranian intermediate EFL learners' oral proficiency examination. *Studies in English Language Teaching* 5(1), 86-108.
- Krashen, S. D. (1987). *Principles and practice in second language acquisition*. New York. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/CCdH6x>, (accessed last 14 December 2015).
- Lee, S., & Carpenter, R. E. (2017). Design and pitch: introducing multiliteracies through scientific research posters. *The Writing Center Journal*, 36(2), 205-232. <https://doi.org/10.7771/2832-9414.1832>
- Li C., Dewaele J. M. (2021). How classroom environment and general grit predict foreign language classroom anxiety of Chinese EFL students. *J. Psychol. Lang. Learning* 3, 86–98. doi: 10.52598
- Li, P., & Pan, G. (2009). The Relationship between motivation and achievement—A survey of the study motivation of English majors in Qingdao Agricultural University. *English Language Teaching*, 2(1), 123. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/ksfWqJ>, (accessed last 14 December 2015).
- Lian, L. H. & Budin, M. B. (2014). Investigating the relationship between English language anxiety and the achievement of school based oral English test among Malaysian form four students.
- Llurda, E. (2018). *Anxiety and foreign language learning: A critical review of the research*. Cambridge University Press.
- Madzlan, N. A., Seng, G. H., & Kesevan, H. V. (2020). Use of video blogs in alleviating public speaking anxiety among ESL learners. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 7(1), 93-99. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.509.2020.71.93.99>
- Mestan, T. (2017). Speaking Anxiety among Different Grades of K12: 6th, 8th, 10th and 12th Grades. Retrieved at <https://doaj.org/article/3e204f4cedc24f0aba0151712e888434>
- Mohamed Khalifa Gawi E. (2020). The impact of foreign language classroom anxiety on Saudi male students' performance at Albaha university. *AWEJ* 11, 258–274. doi: 10.24093/awej/vol11no2.18
- Mohamed Khalifa Gawi, E. (2020). The impact of foreign language classroom anxiety on Saudi male students' performance at Albaha university. *AWEJ* 11, 258–274. doi: 10.24093/awej/vol11no2.18
- Morgan, D. L. (2011). Focus group interviewing. In J. F. Gubrium, & J. A. Holstein (Eds.), *Handbook of interviewing research: Context & Method* (pp. 141–159). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Inc.
- Nada, T., & Tewero, T. (2022). Using design thinking to enhance oral presentation instructions in an advanced level English teaching: A reflective practice. *Journal for Research Scholars and Professionals of English Language Teaching*, 6(29). <https://doi.org/10.54850/jrspelt.6.29.06>
- Nair, M. (2023, October 19). Types of communication | Tips for online students | UoPeople. University of the People. <https://www.uopeople.edu/blog/types-of-communication-back-to-basics/>
- Navaz, A. M. M. Sahna Banu, M. A. (2019.). South eastern University of Sri Lanka: A study on language anxiety among the ESL a study on language anxiety among the ESL undergraduates at the south eastern University of

- Sri Lanka. E-Repository - South Eastern University of Sri Lanka. <https://ir.lib.seu.ac.lk/handle/123456789/4120>
- Nurwahyuni, A. (2019). The impact of clinical pathway implementation on length of stay and hospital cost: A systematic review. In 6th International Conference on Public Health 2019 (pp. 388-396). Sebelas Maret University.
- Ran, Z. O. U., Zeb, S., Nisar, F., Yasmin, F., Poulouva, P., and Haider, S. A. (2022). The impact of emotional intelligence on career decision-making difficulties and generalized self-efficacy among university students in China. *Psychol. Res. Behav. Manag.* 15:865. doi: 10.2147/PRBM.S358742
- Rao, P. S. (2019). The importance of speaking skills in English classrooms. *Alford Council of International English & Literature Journal (ACIELJ)*, 2(2), 6-18.
- Ritchie, H. (2019, June 13). Gender Ratio. Our World inData. <https://ourworldindata.org/gender-ratio#sex-ratio-at-birth>
- Rudiansyah, M. et al. (2016). The Correlation between Serum Iron Level and Transferrin Saturation with Reticulocyte Hemoglobin Equivalent (RET-He) in Routine Hemodialysis. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352028765_The_Correlation_between_Serum_Iron_Level_and_Transferrin_Saturation_with_Reticulocyte_Hemoglobin_Equivalent_RET-He_in_Routine_Hemodialysis
- Sahid, S., Aldiansyah, A., & Iskandar, I. (2018). Understanding gender differences in students' anxiety in a seminar presentation. *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation (IJHI)*, 1(1), 35-46. doi:10.33750/ijhi.v1i1.6. Retrieved July 12, 2019 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325343837_Understanding_Gender_Differences_in_Students'_Anxiety_in_a_Seminar_Presentation.
- Salem, A. A. (2019). A Sage on a stage, to express and impress: TED Talks for improving oral presentation skills, vocabulary retention and its impact on reducing speaking anxiety in ESP settings. *English Language Teaching*, 12(6), 146-160. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v12n6p146>
- Sarani, A., Najjarbaghseyyah, R., & Vaezi, M. N. (2019). The contribution of gender and teaching experience to Iranian EFL Teachers' perceptions of critical pedagogy. *Journal of Modern Research in English Language Studies*, 6(2), 79–101. <https://doi.org/10.30479/jmrels.2019.10595.1328>
- Saricoban, G. & Saricoban, A. (2012). Atatürk and the History of Foreign Language Education in Turkey. *The Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 8 (1), 24-49.
- Selvam, J. S., Das, A. K., & Samuel, M. (2016). Language anxiety and its relationship to self-deprecation among ESL learners in the Philippines. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 12(2), 45-62.
- Shukor, S. S., & Madzlan, N. A. (2022). Gender interaction between covariates in managing anxiety via vlogs. *Journal of Nusantara Studies (JONUS)*, 7(2), 1-20. <http://dx.doi.org/10.24200/jonus.vol7iss2pp1-20>
- Soomro, B.A., Shah, N. and Mangi, S. (2019), "Factors affecting entrepreneurial leadership in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) of Pakistan: empirical evidence", *World Journal of*

Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development, Vol. 15
No. 1, pp. 31-44.

- Taylor, M., Neal, A., Schellinger, J., Ostrowski, S., White, A., Rodriguez, M., ... & Tiller, E. (2020). Examining change in student anxiety and depression after the first year of a professional program secondary to perceived stress: a cross-sectional descriptive study. *Journal of Medical Education*, In Press (In Press). <https://doi.org/10.5812/jme.103404>
- Tian, S., & Mahmud, M. (2018). A study of academic oral presentation anxiety and strategy employment of EFL graduate students. *Indonesian Journal of EFL and Linguistics*, 3(2), 149-170. <https://doi.org/10.21462/ijefl.v3i2.78>
- Tóth, Z. (2021). Two heads better than one? Pair presentation in the EFL classroom—A panacea for anxiety? *European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 5(5), 103-128. <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejfl.v5i5.3921>
- Tujuba, D. E., & Davidson, M. L. (2017). The causes of poor command of English language and its impact on the academic achievements of first year students of Adama science and technology *International Journal of Research in ...*, 7(5), 416–429. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ijr&volume=7&issue=5&article=030>
- Tumapon, M. A. (2019). Teacher identity and language classroom practices: Impact on language anxiety among Filipino ESL learners during oral presentations. *Philippine ESL Journal*, 31(1), 58-74.
- Young, D. J. (2016). An investigation of students' perspectives on anxiety and speaking. *Foreign Language Annals*
- Zhang, L. J. (2001). ESL students' classroom anxiety. *Teaching and Learning*, 21(2), 51-62.